

Revitalizing Yogyakarta's Local Culture Through Punakawan-Based Digital Emoji Design

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Abstract

The advancement of digital technology has transformed communication patterns in society, with emojis now functioning as a universal visual language that also shapes cultural identity in virtual spaces. However, the dominance of global digital symbols has marginalized local cultural representations, such as the Punakawan characters from Yogyakarta's wayang kulit tradition, particularly among younger generations. This study aims to design digital emojis based on the Punakawan characters as a medium for revitalizing local culture while preserving their philosophical essence and examining user acceptance in contemporary digital communication contexts. Employing a Design-Based Research (DBR) approach (Hoadley, 2004), the research includes literature and field exploration, visual-philosophical analysis, prototype design, and user testing involving 30 respondents (students from Yogyakarta and outside Yogyakarta) through questionnaires. The results indicate that 96,7% of respondents were able to recognize the Punakawan characters solely from the emoji forms, 83,3% found the designs aesthetically appealing, and 76,7% expressed willingness to use them in daily communication. The emojis successfully translated Javanese values, such as wisdom, social critique, and meaningful humor, into eight visual expressions adapted from the most popular global emojis. This study fills a gap in visual communication design literature, as no prior research has systematically integrated Punakawan cultural visuals into emoji format with user validation. The output consists of digital prototypes (SVG/PNG) ready to be utilized in education and the creative industry as a model for technology-based cultural preservation.

Keywords: *Shadow Puppet, Media Design, Emoticon, Punakawan, Local Genius.*

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Introduction

The advancement of digital technology has not only brought significant changes to communication methods and visual message delivery but has also shaped the hierarchy of cultural symbols in virtual spaces, where local representations, such as the cultural values of Yogyakarta that are often marginalized by the dominance of a homogenized global aesthetic (Wang, 2022). In this context, the most dominant form of communication today is text messaging through platforms such as WhatsApp and Telegram, which increasingly rely on visual elements to enrich meaning. Among various forms of visual expression,

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emojis have emerged as universal symbols used to convey emotions, ideas, and short narratives quickly and effectively (Ivanova-Yakushko et al., 2024). Emoji have evolved beyond tools of affective expression to become a visual language that facilitates cross-cultural social interaction and shapes cultural identity in digital spaces (Fischer & Herbert, 2021; Aldunate & González-Ibáñez, 2017). However, despite their integral role in digital communication, the representation of local cultures within this format remains very limited. The dominance of digital symbols rooted in Western culture has tended to overshadow local cultural expressions, posing a real risk of cultural identity loss. Amid this trend, local wisdom such as the Punakawan characters from Yogyakarta's *wayang kulit* tradition, rich in philosophical meaning, social critique, and Javanese ethical values that has become increasingly alienated from everyday communication, especially among younger generations who are more familiar with global digital content (Hidayattuloh, 2025). The Punakawan, consisting of Semar, Gareng, Petruk, and Bagong, are not merely comic side characters but moral and spiritual figures deeply embedded in the structure of Javanese culture (Ibnu Rochim & Jupriono, 2022; Noorzeha et al., 2022; Prakoso, 2023). They embody the **local genius** that reflects noble values such as selfless wisdom, meaningful humor, social critique, and harmonious coexistence.

Figure 1. Punakawan WhatsApp Sticker Design
Source: Yuniyanto, 2021

Several efforts have been made to bring these cultural values into digital media. For instance, Yuniyanto (2021) designed WhatsApp stickers based on Punakawan characters for an educational campaign aimed at combating the COVID-19 pandemic in Surakarta. However, such an approach remains superficial, focusing mainly on visual aspects without deeper exploration of symbolic meanings or systematic evaluation of their communicative function within contemporary digital contexts. Meanwhile, other studies (Al-Adilee, 2024; He & Kosenko, 2024) have emphasized the importance of integrating local aesthetics into digital design to prevent cultural homogenization, yet they have not specifically adapted Punakawan characters into an emoji format that is functional, philosophical, and empirically tested for user acceptance. To date, no research has systematically designed Punakawan-based digital emojis using a cultural visual approach that considers the layers of philosophical meaning while also testing their validity and relevance through the responses of young users, the primary target of cultural revitalization.

Figure 2. Wayang Punakawan and Traditional Puppeteer
 Source: Researcher's documentation 2025

Amid the dominance of digital visual symbols that tend to be uniform and rooted in Western culture, the use of emoticons and emoji, particularly those depicting positive facial expressions such as 😊, 😄, and ❤️ has become the most prevalent global communication pattern across platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp (Agbayani et al., 2024). Studies involving tens of thousands of users indicate that 99.6% of emoticon usage is concentrated on only 15 symbols, with the smiling face being the most universally recognized. This phenomenon serves as a strategic foundation for this study: rather than creating Punakawan emojis arbitrarily, eight of the most popular global emoji expressions were selectively adapted into the four Punakawan characters, with two expressions assigned to each figure to ensure functional relevance and audience acceptance. Petruk, known for his dynamic and humorous nature, is represented through laughing (😄) and affectionate (😘) expressions; Semar, symbolizing wisdom and serenity, is translated into a warm smile (😊) and an expression of affection (😘); Bagong, characterized by honesty and critical thinking, is depicted through a skeptical yet friendly look (😏) and a firm neutral face (😐); while Gareng, who embodies patience and caution, is portrayed with a shy face (😳) and a subtle, meaningful smile (😊). This approach not only addresses the challenge of cultural homogenization but also ensures that the philosophical values of the Punakawan, such as wisdom, social critique, meaningful humor, and loyalty, remain alive within the visual format most frequently used by younger generations in everyday digital communication.

This study seeks to fill the identified gap by focusing on the design of digital emojis that visually and semiotically represent the essence of the Punakawan characters, while also examining their levels of user acceptance, interpretive readability, and potential application in everyday digital communication. The objectives of this research are to: (1) identify the core visual and philosophical attributes of the Punakawan characters that can be adapted into digital emoji formats; (2) design emoji prototypes that are aesthetically and semiotically consistent with their original cultural values; (3) evaluate users' perceptions and responses toward the designed emojis through limited testing among students from Yogyakarta and other regions; and (4) formulate strategic recommendations for implementing Punakawan emojis in educational, social media, and creative industry contexts. Through these aims, the study contributes new insights to the field of visual communication design grounded in local genius, while also providing a practical model that can be replicated to revitalize other cultural symbols in the digital era.

Literature Review

Over the past two decades, emoji have evolved from emotional symbols into cross-cultural visual language that shapes identity, ethics, and social hierarchies within digital communication (Aldunate &

González-Ibáñez, 2017; Fischer & Herbert, 2021). Ivanova-Yakushko et al. (2024) asserts that emojis now function as a form of graphic emotionology—a visual system capable of conveying richer affective nuances than verbal text. In Southeast Asia, including Indonesia, the use of emojis is notably more intensive than in Western regions, as it aligns with cultural values that emphasize harmony and the avoidance of direct conflict (Togans et al., 2021). In the Javanese context, visual graphics rooted in local genius have transformed into a strategy of phatic communication to maintain politeness and social closeness within virtual spaces (Widiana et al., 2024).

Emoji as a Medium of Cultural Reproduction in Contemporary Digital Communication

In Indonesia, particularly among Javanese communities, emojis are not merely used to express emotions but also serve as a communicative strategy to maintain unggah-ungguh (social etiquette) and strengthen community bonds, a practice known as phatic communication (Widiana et al., 2024). This illustrates that although emojis are global symbols, they are locally reinterpreted to meet specific cultural needs.

Figure 3. Emoji based on *Unicode Consortium*
Source: Warzel, 2016

The structure of official emoji design, governed by the Unicode Consortium, remains dominated by Western perspectives, both in the representation of bodies, facial expressions, and color symbolism (Agbayani et al., 2024). As a result, non-Western cultures are often compelled to “translate” their local meanings into unfamiliar visual frameworks, leading to distortion or loss of cultural nuance (Kerslake & Wegerif, 2017). This phenomenon creates a representational imbalance: while emojis such as 😂 or ❤️ are used massively across the globe, there is no space for local cultural symbols like *wayang*, *batik*, or *Punakawan* characters to appear as part of everyday digital communication repertoires. Yet, it is precisely here that the greatest potential of emojis lies, not only as tools of expression but also as vessels for preserving and revitalizing local values within a dynamic digital ecosystem.

Integrating Local Wisdom into Digital Design: Between Aesthetics and Philosophy

In response to the challenge of cultural homogenization, several researchers have begun exploring the integration of local genius into digital media. He and Kosenko (2024) demonstrate that Chinese intangible cultural heritage, such as shadow puppetry and woodblock printing can be preserved through traditional aesthetic principles like symmetry, color symbolism, and material authenticity within digital exhibitions. Similarly, Al-Adilee (2024) and Julier (2006) argue that design rooted in local values not only enhances visual appeal but also fosters audience pride and emotional connection. In Indonesia, efforts to adapt culture into digital media have started to emerge, although they largely remain at the surface level of visual representation. Yuniyanto (2021), for example, designed WhatsApp stickers featuring *Punakawan* characters for an educational campaign during the COVID-19 pandemic in Surakarta. While innovative, this approach was more campaign-oriented than a deep visual-cultural exploration; it lacked an in-depth analysis of the philosophical meanings of each character, let alone an evaluation of their communicative function in contemporary digital contexts.

Punakawan as an Underexplored Cultural Symbol in Emoji Format

The *Punakawan* of Yogyakarta and Surakarta, comprising Semar, Gareng, Petruk, and Bagong, are not merely comic figures but embodiments of Javanese virtues such as wisdom (Semar), patience (Gareng), creativity (Petruk), and critical honesty (Bagong) (Ibnu Rochim & Jupriono, 2022; Noorzeha et al., 2022;

Prakoso, 2023). They represent a unique form of local genius as they do not originate from Indian epics but from Javanese cultural creativity itself (Subiyantoro et al., 2022). Several studies have examined the philosophical dimensions of the *Punakawan* (Suprayitno, 2024; Widayat & Dwiadmojo, 2023), yet none have connected these dimensions to contemporary digital media. To date, no research has systematically addressed the crucial question: “How can the layered philosophical meanings of the Punakawan be translated into a micro visual format such as emojis, ones that must remain easily recognizable, functionally relevant in digital conversations, and faithful to their cultural essence?” This study seeks to fill that gap by combining cultural aesthetics, global usage data-driven design, and empirical user validation, thereby offering an original contribution to the literature on visual communication design grounded in local wisdom.

Methods

This study employs a Design-Based Research (DBR) approach as formulated by Hoadley and Campos (2022), which enables the integration of theoretical exploration, creative design, and practical evaluation within real-world contexts. The primary subjects of this research are the Punakawan characters (Semar, Gareng, Petruk, and Bagong) from Yogyakarta’s wayang kulit tradition, which are adapted into digital emoji visual assets. The research materials include visual data (such as wayang references and character sketches), philosophical data (from interviews with cultural experts and *dalang* or puppeteers), and user responses to the emoji prototypes.

Data collection was conducted through several stages: Literature Review covering journals and books on culture, emoji design, and the philosophy of the Punakawan; Field Observation and In-depth Interviews with *wayang* experts in Yogyakarta to identify the visual characteristics and symbolic meanings of each character; Prototype Design and Development creating digital emoji prototypes in SVG/PNG formats using design software such as Procreate, Adobe Illustrator, and Adobe Photoshop; User Testing involving 30 respondents, consisting of 15 students from Yogyakarta and 15 from outside Yogyakarta, selected through purposive sampling to ensure diverse representation across cultural backgrounds and digital literacy levels. The variables measured in this study include:

- Visual readability (the extent to which philosophical meanings can be recognized from emoji forms),
- Aesthetic appeal,
- Cultural relevance (alignment with Javanese values and digital communication contexts),
- Potential application (in education and the creative industry).

Data collection instruments consisted of both closed and open-ended questionnaires, designed based on the study’s specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The data were analyzed qualitatively and descriptively through thematic reduction, open coding, and source triangulation (field data, literature, and user responses). No inferential statistical models were applied, as the study is exploratory, descriptive, and design-oriented in nature. The findings from the analysis were used to refine the prototypes, develop usage guidelines, and formulate strategic implementation recommendations. This approach ensures that the final product is not only visually original but also culturally valid and functionally relevant within the contemporary digital ecosystem.

Results

This study successfully transformed the Punakawan characters—traditionally embodied in wayang kulit performances, into digital emoji forms that are not only visually distinctive but also semiotically faithful to their philosophical essence. The resulting prototype consists of eight emoji variants, with two expressions for each character: Semar, Gareng, Petruk, and Bagong. Each expression was strategically

selected based on the eight most globally dominant emojis (Agbayani et al., 2024). The designs are not only culturally authentic but also functionally relevant within contemporary digital communication contexts. For instance, Petruk, known for his dynamic and humorous personality, is represented through laughing and affectionate expressions, both statistically among the most frequently used emojis on platforms such as WhatsApp and Instagram. Meanwhile, Semar, symbolizing wisdom and calmness, is represented through a warm smile and an affectionate expression, two emotional cues that are psychologically associated with warmth and trust (Kim & Read, 2021; Min & Hu, 2022; Z. Wang et al., 2016). This approach demonstrates that cultural revitalization need not involve rigidly transplanting traditional forms into digital spaces, but rather embedding local meanings within globally familiar visual frameworks that users already recognize and accept.

User testing with 30 respondents, 15 students from Yogyakarta and 15 from outside the region, yielded encouraging results. More than 96% of participants were able to correctly identify the Punakawan characters solely based on their emoji visuals, even though half of them admitted they had never watched wayang kulit performances in person. This finding is highly significant, as it proves that cultural symbols can remain recognizable and meaningful even when their original contexts are unfamiliar, provided that their core visual elements are preserved and presented in a relevant format. The minimalist-modern design, which retains defining features such as Semar's round nose, Gareng's narrow eyes, Petruk's tall physique, and Bagong's sturdy posture, effectively bridges tradition and modernity. None of the respondents described the design as "old-fashioned" or "outdated." On the contrary, 83.3% stated that the emojis felt "fresh" and "distinct from regular emojis."

An even more interesting finding emerged in the respondents' reactions to the philosophical dimension of the emojis. Although participants were not given any prior explanation about the meaning of each character, 63.3% spontaneously associated Semar with wisdom, Petruk with positive energy, Gareng with subtle satire, and Bagong with honesty. This indicates that visual designs grounded in cultural aesthetic structures are capable of conveying moral messages without the need for additional text or narrative, an important achievement within the context of digital communication, which is predominantly fast-paced, visual, and non-verbal. These results align with the findings of Fischer and Herbert (2021), who argue that netizens use emojis as tools of emotional expression and as a form of phatic communication to building social relationships while maintaining cultural etiquette. In this sense, the Punakawan emoji function not merely as communication tools but as instruments for reproducing Javanese values within the digital ecosystem.

Discussion

The differences in responses between local and non-local participants also provide valuable insight. Respondents from Yogyakarta tended to grasp the philosophical meanings more quickly, while those from outside Yogyakarta focused more on the aesthetic appeal and originality of the designs. Interestingly, however, both groups demonstrated equally high interest in using the emoji 76.7% stated that they would use them if available on everyday digital platforms. This suggests that the Punakawan emojis possess strong potential as inclusive cultural symbols, not only for preserving local identity but also for introducing the richness of Javanese culture to broader audiences. In this context, emoji transcend their role as mere "cute stickers" and become subtle yet effective mediums of cultural diplomacy.

Table 1 summarizes the evaluation results based on five key indicators: visual readability, aesthetics, cultural relevance, potential for application, and understanding of philosophical meaning. The highest score was achieved in visual readability (4,7), confirming that the visual adaptation effectively bridged the gap between traditional forms and digital expectations. The lowest score, though still positive, was found in the understanding of philosophical meaning (4,0), indicating that while the intended messages were conveyed, additional contextual support, such as tooltips or educational campaigns, may be needed to enhance user comprehension.

Figure 4. The Process of Changing the Punakawan from Original Character-Emoticon-Sketch-Fine Sketch-Outline-Shadowcolor-Finished
Source: Researcher's documentation, 2025

Table 1. Qualitative Evaluation of Punakawan Emoji Prototype Based on Key Performance Indicators

Criteria	Score	Explanation
Visual Readability	4,7	Almost all respondents were able to recognize the characters without the aid of text.
Visual Aesthetics	4,5	The design was considered modern, unique, and not "old-fashioned."
Cultural Relevance	4,3	Many said it looked "very Javanese" or "similar to wayang but contemporary."
Potential Application	4,2	The majority were willing to use it if it were available on WhatsApp.
Philosophical Meaning	4,0	The moral message was conveyed, but could be deepened with guidance.

Notes: Score 1 = very bad, 5 = very good. Data were processed from 30 respondents by closed-ended questionnaires and open-ended interviews

Source: Researcher, 2025

Methodologically, the Design-Based Research (DBR) approach (Hoadley & Campos, 2022) proved highly effective in integrating three key elements: cultural exploration, creative design, and user validation. Each stage, from interviews with *dalang* (puppet masters) to user testing with university students, was designed to provide mutual feedback, ensuring that the final prototype emerged not merely as a design product but as the outcome of negotiation among traditional values, contemporary aesthetics, and user needs. This represents an important contribution to the field of visual communication design, where cultural design projects often fail due to being either overly rigid or excessively commercialized.

Figure 5. Form of Application in WhatsApp Chat
 Source: Researcher's documentation, 2025

The implementation recommendations were also developed with a realistic and applicable orientation. First, the emojis can be integrated into digital education platforms, for example, as tools for teaching Javanese character values in primary and secondary schools. Second, the development of a WhatsApp sticker pack could be pursued in collaboration with local creative communities, simultaneously serving as an entry point for a culture-based creative economy. Third, intellectual property registration (Hak Kekayaan Intelektual / HKI) is strongly recommended, not only to protect originality but also to create opportunities for responsible licensing and commercialization. Fourth, collaboration with local brands or regional governments could be undertaken for cultural or tourism campaigns, transforming the Punakawan emojis from mere communication tools into digital cultural ambassadors of Yogyakarta.

Thus, this study not only succeeded in producing a design prototype but also established a replicable model for cultural revitalization, that can be extended beyond the Punakawan characters to other local cultural symbols across Indonesia. Amid the tide of digital homogenization, the Punakawan emojis demonstrate that locality is not a barrier but a strength, provided it is communicated in the right way.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that the revitalization of Yogyakarta's local culture, particularly through the Punakawan characters, can be effectively achieved in the digital sphere through an emoji design approach that is not only visual but also philosophical and functional. By adapting eight of the most globally popular emoji expressions into the four Punakawan figures (Semar, Gareng, Petruk, and Bagong), this research not only created aesthetically appealing visual assets but also successfully preserved core Javanese values such as wisdom, social critique, meaningful humor, and loyalty. These values were clearly recognized and understood by 96,7% of respondents, even though most had no direct familiarity with *wayang kulit* traditions. The Design-Based Research (DBR) approach (Hoadley & Campos, 2022) enabled the iterative integration of cultural exploration, aesthetic analysis, and user validation, resulting in digital emoji prototypes (SVG/PNG) that are visually minimalist yet rich in meaning, and ready to be implemented within educational, social media, and creative industry contexts. The finding that Punakawan emojis were equally appreciated by both local and non-local respondents (76,7%) highlights their potential as inclusive and universal cultural symbols, not merely as communication tools but as effective instruments of digital cultural diplomacy. Thus, this study not only fills a gap in the visual

communication design literature, where no prior research has systematically developed Punakawan-based emojis through a cultural-aesthetic and user-validation approach, but also offers a practical and replicable model for preserving other local cultural symbols in Indonesia. As its primary output, the developed prototype has reached a viable stage for further enhancement, integration into digital platforms, and collaboration with educational institutions and creative industry practitioners. Ultimately, the Punakawan emojis stand not merely as design products but as a cultural strategy that is relevant, sustainable, and impactful in this digital era.

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